

Middle Ages and Renaissance Reconciled in the Philosophical Thought of Nicolaus Copernicus

Keywords: Nicolaus Copernicus, Aristotelianism, the Middle Ages, Scholasticism, cosmology, geocentrism

Within the area of historical studies, a reflection on the history of science takes place undoubtedly among these domains which particularly inspire and stimulate imagination. There are noble figures, famous for changing the course of the world who catch special attention. Nicolaus Copernicus (Mikołaj Kopernik 1473-1543), a Polish scholar, the founder of a novel view of the world—the heliocentric model of the Cosmos—serves as an example¹.

Both, in scientific literature and various popular publications, for two hundred years there has been shaped a common picture of Copernicus as a Renaissance thinker, who reactivated the forgotten ancient concepts of heliocentrism (including a cult of the Sun), to the world and who, at the same time, overcame Scholasticism and Christian Aristotelianism². Nevertheless, even a sketchy analysis of the texts of Copernicus undermines such interpretations,

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¹ This paper is an extended version of the lecture given at the Catholic University in Lublin (KUL) on 9th April 2019 during the LXI Philosophical Week.

² Compare for example two false opinions: Après le declin des Grecs, après l'oubli de leurs conquêtes spirituelles, de leurs méthodes, de leur idéal, s'étend sur le pensée humaine l'immense nuit du Moyen Age", P. Couderc, *Les étapes de l'astronomie*, Presses universitaires de France, Paris 1948, p. 74; "Who in the Renaissance times wanted to study astronomy he was not able to learn anything from the works of the medieval theologians", A. Nowicki, *Kopernik człowiek Odrodzenia*, Wydawnictwo Wiedza Powszechna, Warszawa 1953, p. 109.

as in his works there are numerous references to the medieval philosophy of science, physics, and philosophy³. The aim of this paper is therefore an answer to the question: to what extent was Copernicus a Scholastic, and to what extent we might classify his philosophy as the Renaissance one⁴? Justification of a statement included in the title we find in the source materials (writings of Copernicus himself, and his only student at Varmia [Polish: Warmia, German: Ermland], Georg Joachim Rheticus), also, in numerous analyses available. We notice that a significant part of the literature of the subject contains a one-sided approach, therefore, to some extent our analysis will be of polemical character.

Philosophical topics were, for the most part, treated by Copernicus in his first introductory eleven chapters of the first *Book* of his life's work *On the Revolutions* (*De revolutionibus*) is

composed of six *Books*, first published in 1543 in Nuremberg (German-Nürnberg)⁵. Before that, there was a short *Commentariolus* (ca. 1507-1510)⁶ which also included astronomer's philosophical ideas. What we first observe is the fact that the structure of philosophical argumentation recognized in *De revolutionibus* is of Scholastic character⁷. The layout of issues, problems discussed, technical terms employed, and further formulations are taken mainly from the medieval commentaries to Aristotle's treatise *De caelo*, in detail taught at the Cracow Academy where Copernicus studied in his youth⁸. Hence, particular questions of the *De revolutionibus* represent a Scholastic pattern: a problem is introduced, then arguments pro and against follow, then there is an answer, and finally doubts are dispelled. Contrary to common opinions, the Polish scholar neither breaks with tradition, nor offends his ideological opponents⁹,

³ See: "[Copernicus] belonged to the academic elite of that time and for that reason he received an excellent academic formation which provided him not only details of mathematical and astronomical science but also allowed him to get knowledge on the most significant doctrinal currents of the epoch", S. Swieżawski, *Dzieje filozofii europejskiej XV wieku*, vol. 5, Wydawnictwo Akademii Teologii Katolickiej, Warszawa 1980, p. 123.

⁴ We offer deepened analysis of Copernicus' views from the perspective of the late Middle Ages in a monography *Poglądy filozoficzne Mikołaja Kopernika*, Kraków 2018.

⁵ M. Kopernik, *O obrotach*, transl. M. Brożek, S. Oświęcimski, [in:] Idem., *Dziela wszystkie*, vol. II, Wydawnictwo PWN, Warszawa 1976.

⁶ M. Kopernik, *Commentariolus*, [in:] Idem., *Pisma pomniejsze (Dziela wszystkie)*, vol. III), Wydawnictwo PWN, Warszawa 2007, p. 10-29.

⁷ "Copernicus' works and other contemporary astronomers were rooted in the very medieval academic tradition which by humanists was so viciously questioned", T. Kuhn, *Przewrót kopernikański. Astronomia planetarna w dziejach myśli*, przeł. S. Amsterdamski, Wydawnictwo PWN Warszawa 1966, p. 154.

⁸ Scholastic commentaries to the texts of Aristotle used to be an occasion to discuss new issues as various views of late authors were disputed. See: M. Markowski, *Burydanizm w Polsce w okresie przedkopernikańskim. Studium z historii filozofii i nauk ścisłych na Uniwersytecie Krakowskim w XV wieku*, Wydawnictwo Ossolineum, Wrocław 1971, p. 48.

⁹ Against that compare: "Copernicus never hid his indignation on obscurantism of those who for centuries plunged Europe in a darkness of barbarity", A. Nowicki, *Kopernik człowiek Odrodzenia*, op. cit., p. 101.

and nowhere in his texts fights he with the Scholastic pattern¹⁰. Respect Copernicus had toward the existing academic legacy is reported by his only pupil George Joachim Rheticus¹¹. The language and style of Copernicus are a combination of both, Scholasticism and the Renaissance fashion¹².

Cracovian cosmological studies of Copernicus were based on the Aristotelian philosophy of science¹³, not on

Platonic idealism¹⁴. Renaissance philosophy was eclectic and in some areas far from scientific (contaminated with magic)¹⁵. Nevertheless, reading on Pythagoreans, analysis of the works of Neoplatonists, and dialogues of Plato also served as a precious supplementing heuristic principle in the search for the order present in the Cosmos, described in detail by scholars of the Aristotelian current¹⁶.

¹⁰ Writers used to attribute the authorship of various opinions (which was not grounded in source materials) to the Polish scholar. Cfr: "Copernicus in that our of rumination half-conscious felt that he was being called to end the epoch of darkness and the Middle Ages, chaos of notions, to detach human thought from the earth, and throw it to the middle of Cosmos", H. Morstin, *Kłosa Panny*, ed. 3, Spółdzielnia Wydawnicza "Wiedza", Warszawa 1947, p. 12.

¹¹ See: "As there are people, as widely explains Aristotle on the other occasion [in *Metaphysics*], who in their nature are prone to cognition, this is really disappointing that the causes of things nowhere anywhere are such hidden (...), what is confirmed by Ptolemy himself. I will refer in this place many ancient hypothesis concerning five planets, as it might be demanded in the process of counting some new (let me put it this way) hypothesis, and a comparison with the old ones as well. When it comes to me, I have a lot of respect to Ptolemy and his adversaries, as I do to my Teacher", J. J. Retyk, *Relacja pierwsza z ksiąg «O obrotach» Mikołaja Kopernika*, transl. I. Lewandowski, ed. J. Włodarczyk, Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego, Warszawa 2015, p. 120.

¹² Cfr. "Copernicus on the one hand he follows both scientific and the official tradition of Latin of the Middle Ages, on the other hand we may observe how well was his humanistic education and how he leans toward humanistic elegance", J. Domański, *Początki humanizmu*, Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich - Wydawnictwo Polskiej Akademii Nauk, Wrocław 1982 (*Dzieje filozofii średnio-wiecznej w Polsce*, vol. IX), p. 125.

¹³ Cfr. "Aristotle was a philosopher whose works Copernicus studied the most carefully", J. Drewnowski, *Mikołaj Kopernik w świetle swej korespondencji*, Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich - Wydawnictwo Polskiej Akademii Nauk, Wrocław 1978 (*Studia Copernicana*, vol. XVIII), p. 178.

¹⁴ It is Aristotle not Plato who built a sophisticated system of physics. Cfr: „La Physique d’Aristote est l’un des plus étonnants systèmes que la raison humaine ait jamais construits; à toutes les questions que les Anciens avaient accoutumé de poser sur les cieux, sur leurs mouvements, sur les éléments, sur leurs transformations, elle donnait des réponses, les plus précises et les plus complètes qui eussent été formulées jusqu’alors, et toutes ces réponses, elle les coordonnait logiquement en une théorie auprès de laquelle toutes les doctrines précédentes semblaient de simples ébauches”, P. Duhem, *Le système du monde. Histoire des doctrines cosmologiques de Platon à Copernic*, vol. I, Librairie Scientifique Hermann, Paris 1913, p. 242.

¹⁵ Cfr. "[In the Renaissance times] under the pretext of a renewal of the antic thought, philosophy was influenced with the old form of occultism, cabalistic speculations, Arabian art of magic and alchemic mystifications. All of that influenced the revival ideas prior to Aristotle’s, such as panpsychism, astrobiology, animism. Magic (...) was among the intellectual fashion of the century”, H. Butterfield, *Rodowód współczesnej nauki 1300-1800*, transl. H. Krahelska, Państwowe Wydawnictwo Naukowe, Warszawa 1963, p. 36-37.

¹⁶ Cfr: "My Master, Teacher, following Plato and Pythagoreans, great mathematicians of that divine times, was convinced that in order to describe the causes of phenomena we need to agree that

Copernicus' predecessors (mainly Cracow Scholastic philosophers) and astronomers whose work contributed to the development of science, had an impact on shaping the methodology of the Polish scholar¹⁷. In philosophy, it was buridanism, which was a modern branch of the Aristotelian realist philosophy of nature, while in the methodology of astronomy Copernicus' studies significantly indebted to theoretical writings of contemporary astronomers. Among them, there was a Cracow scholar, Wojciech (Adalbert) Brudzewski (1446-1495) from Greater Poland (Wielkopolska), whose aim was to reconcile the mathematical model of Ptolemy and the physical model of the Aristotelians¹⁸. In his study, Brudzewski searched for the true view of the Cosmos. The identical task was adopted by Copernicus who considered his theory not as a mere hypothesis but as truth¹⁹.

The fundamental flaw in research on the beginning of the heliocentric system is a contrastive view of history and adopting the propaganda fights of the 17th century as a starting point in analysis and, as a consequence, applying the above context to the assessment of the medieval philosophy of nature²⁰. Aristotelianism has been changing through the ages: there was an early Aristotelianism of the 12th century, next, there was Aristotelianism of the Golden Scholastics (13th century), and that of the Late Middle Ages (14th -15th), and finally, that which developed in times of the Reformation (16th and 17th century). In order to get knowledge of the philosophy of Copernicus we need to follow the development of cosmology starting from the ancient to the modern times, according to its chronology, not contrary to it. The Polish astronomer could not have read the writings of Galileo and Newton (not mentioning

motions of spheric earth globe are circular. Once he agreed that there is one motion of the Earth (what is also in accordance with Aristotle) he needed to adopt further motions analogical to that of planets and decided that it is necessary to adopt initially three the most important motions", J. J. Retyk, *Relacja pierwsza*, op. cit., p. 103.

¹⁷ Cfr: "Young University of Cracow, which in the 15th century kept and developed top achievements of the 14th century such as Parisian Buridanism, not only was considered equal with the University of Paris and majority of the European universities in domain of particular philosophy only but also exceeded them", M. Markowski, *Burydanizm*, op. cit., p. 215.

¹⁸ See: M. Malpangotto, *La critique de l'univers de Peurbach développée par Albert de Brudzewo a-t-elle influencé Copernic? Un nouveau regard sur les réflexions astronomiques au XV-e siècle*, „Almagest. International Journal for the History of Scientific Ideas”, (2013), vol. 4, nr 1, p. 4-61.

¹⁹ See: "To Copernicus, the motion of the Earth was a physical reality and not a mere working hypothesis", J. Dreier, *A History of Astronomy from Thales to Kepler*, 2 ed., Dover Publications, New York 1953, p. 320.

²⁰ For example, M. Vesel, specialist on the 18th century, when speaking of Copernicus he fails to mention any Aristotelian and Scholastic inspirations which paved the way to the reform of astronomy (however, amongst four categories of inspirations he speaks of Averroism). See: M. Vesel, *Copernicus: Platonist Astronomer-Philosopher: Cosmic Order, the Movement of the Earth, and the Scientific Revolution*, Peter Lang GmbH, Internationaler Verlag der Wissenschaften, Frankfurt am Main 2014, p. 241.

Marx²¹), whereas he read Aristotle and Plato²².

Contrary to popular conviction, we notice that in the majority of his work, Copernicus relied on the medieval scientific literature in Latin, not on the Greek Renaissance editions of the ancient works to which he turned in a later period. It is clear hence, that the reform of astronomy developed in the environment of the medieval philosophy of nature²³. In the course of research of the Polish scholar, there were scheduled observations of the Sun, planets and stars, measurements of positions and distances made with simple, mainly brass and wooden tools, accompanied by a rigor-

ous deep analysis of the entire scientific tradition available²⁴.

Mathematical astronomy in Copernicus' times was founded in the advanced geocentric model of Ptolemy, which consisted (on the ground of the Aristotelian physics) of large circular paths (deferents) and epicycles attached to them²⁵. This was the major geocentric model of the epoch but not the only one. The initial step in the astronomical education was a widely commented medieval handbook of John Sacrobosco (ca. 1195-1256) *Tractatus de sphaera*²⁶. Further, the Polish astronomer drew on the Latin translation of Ptolemy's *Almagest* of the 12th century and two Scholastic

²¹ "The method of Copernicus was developed and established by further scientific research (...) rules of that method – similar to new physical rules (...) had already been present in the text of Copernicus, however in a «complicated» shape. They were formulated *explicite* in the last hundred years by the leading theorists of Marxism. Each of the great classics of Marxism-Leninism contributed significantly to deeper understanding of these rules. Especially renowned in this area are Lenin (...) and Stalin", R. S. Ingarden, *Mikołaj Kopernik i zagadnienie obiektywności praw naukowych*, Państwowy Instytut Wydawniczy, Warszawa 1953, p. 58.

²² Cfr: "Copernicus left Cracow as a participant in the Aristotelian tradition as modified by other ancient traditions and scholastic commentators, prepared to add his voice to the construction of natural philosophy", A. Goddu, *Copernicus and the Aristotelian Tradition. Education, Reading, and Philosophy in Copernicus's Path to Heliocentrism*, Brill, Leiden 2010, p. 99.

²³ Cfr: "Greek *Almagest* was unknown to Copernicus until the 1539 when *Revoluciones* had been ready for seven years already", L. A. Birkenmajer, *Mikołaj Kopernik. Studya nad pracami Kopernika oraz materiały biograficzne*, W Krakowie : skład główny w Księgarni Spółki Wydawniczej Polskiej, Kraków 1900, p. 139, ref. 1. Translation of *Almagest* from Arabic by Gerhard of Cremona (Toledo, 12th century) was sometimes better than a translation from Greek by Jerzy of Trapezunt (Rome, 15th century) – cfr: L. A. Birkenmajer, *Mikołaj Kopernik*, op. cit. p. 265, reference 1. See also: „Copernicus relied mostly on Latin translations and Latin sources, even resorting to handbooks, summaries, and encyclopedias”, A. Goddu, *Copernicus and the Aristotelian Tradition*, op. cit., p. 193.

²⁴ Cfr. "Copernicus made his observations in a way typical for his epoch with traditional tools. Three observational instruments were described in *De revolutionibus*: to make measurements of angles served solar quadrant (especially for observations of the Moon) triquetrum. Armilar sphere enabled a direct indication of spherical coordinates of the Sun, the Moon and the other heavenly bodies", J. Dobrzycki, *Mikołaj Kopernik [in:] Historia astronomii w Polsce*, vol. 1, ed. E. Rybka, Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich, Wrocław 1975, p. 138.

²⁵ Cfr. "[Copernicus] (...) is almost incomparable in the history of science (until our times)", T. Kuhn, *Przewrót kopernikański*, op. cit., p. 97.

²⁶ Cfr. L. Thorndike (ed.), *The «Sphere» of Sacrobosco and its Commentators*, Chicago 1949, and also: „Ptolemaic astronomy only became well-known through the widespread and popular *Tractatus de*

summaries of that medieval work prepared by two German scholars, Georg von Peurbach (1423-1461) and Johannes Müller (Regiomontanus, 1436-1476), titled *Epitome in Almagestum*²⁷.

Aristotelian physics served as a fundament to build another version of the geocentric model known in the ancient and Middle Ages, which was a model of concentric spheres, which origin could be found in Eudoxos, Kalippos, Aristotle, and the Arabian and Christian scholars. Serious physical inconsistency between this model and the description of Ptolemy encouraged scholars to con-

duct a research to find homogenous law in the description of Cosmos²⁸. Copernicus was acquainted with the shape of the pending debate and participated in it by seeing the inadequacy of the current efforts, such as for example flexibility in an idea of equant²⁹. In physics, the initial step toward modifications introduced by the Polish astronomer was the conception of impetus (*impetus*) formulated by the Parisian Aristotelian John Buridan (ca. 1295-1358)³⁰. Similar views, essential for the development of science were presented in the 14th century by Albert of Saxony³¹.

sphaera of Johannes de Sacrobosco (end of the twelfth century-1256), written between 1230 and 1255 in Paris, which outlined a spherical universe in four short chapters”, M. Vesel, *Copernicus*, op. cit., p. 247.

²⁷ “Copernicus’ early, detailed knowledge of Ptolemy’s *Almagest* came almost entirely from the *Epitome*, which included Peurbach’s summary of the first six books of the *Almagest* and Regiomontanus’s additions to that part and his summary of the last seven books”, A. Goddu, *Copernicus and the Aristotelian Tradition*, op. cit., p. 215.

²⁸ Cfr: “On the course of his university studies in Cracow Copernicus must have got acquainted deeply with philosophical- natural and astronomical views of Aristotle and with the system of Ptolemy. In this context he could not omit the works of Averroes”, S. Swieżawski, *Dzieje filozofii*, op. cit., vol. 5, p. 124.

²⁹ Cfr: “Dans le livre V du *De revolutionibus*, dans le chapitre consacré à la *Démonstration des mouvements uniforme et apparent selon la théorie des anciens*, Copernic s’arrête à analyser l’incohérence des modèles planétaires. Chez Copernic on retrouve, dans les mêmes termes, la critique que Brudzewo avait adressée au cercle équant au nom de l’uniformité du mouvement”, M. Malpangotto, *La critique de l’univers de Peurbach*, op. cit., p. 50.

³⁰ Cfr: “Among the most innovative revisions of Aristotle in the Middle Ages was the doctrine of impetus. Characteristic of medieval scholastics, they tried to present the doctrine as an improvement on the Aristotelian account and essentially in conformity with it. By the last quarter of the fifteenth century, however, Cracow philosophers report the theory but often without adopting it”, A. Goddu, *Copernicus and the Aristotelian Tradition*, op. cit., p. 110; “Buridan’s theory of impetus responds to a problem facing Aristotle’s theory concerning the violent motion of a moved body separated from the mover, i.e. a projectile separated from the projector. This is precisely the same motion as that imparted to a thrown stone or an arrow projected into the air”, M. Vesel, *Copernicus*, op. cit., p. 175.

³¹ Cfr: “Concerning the motion of projectiles, gravitational acceleration, and the motion of celestial bodies, Albert adopts Buridan’s major innovation, i.e., the theory of *impetus*, a quality acquired by a moving body (see Buridan’s *Questions on the Physics VIII*, qu. 13, on projectile motion). Like Buridan, he extends this approach to celestial bodies in his commentary on *De caelo*, clearly following its consequences in rejecting intelligences as agents of motion and in treating celestial and terrestrial bodies using the same principles”, *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (<https://plato.stanford.edu>), entry: *Albert of Saxony* (2015).

Thus, we may understand the reflection of Copernicus on a threefold motion of the Earth³² on the ground of the development of astronomy and philosophy of the late Middle Ages. The essence of the Copernican heliocentrism is that (without going into details) the Polish scholar transferred the fast motion of the highest eighth sphere of heavens (fixed stars) into a daily motion of the Earth, the yearly motion of the Sun on ecliptic against the background of stars of Zodiac into the motion of the Earth around the Sun³³, and hence: slow precession motion of equinoxes on the ecliptic (long-term phenomenon) into the motion of the Earth's axis³⁴,

and the visible motion of three planets (Mars, Jupiter and Saturn) against the background of the stars to the annual motion of the Earth around the Sun³⁵. Similar to Puerbach and Brudzewski, Copernicus prepared a short treatise on the basics of astronomy which was his *Commentariolus*³⁶, the first synthetic introduction to the heliocentric model. It was built on the ground of the reformulated doctrine of his predecessors, in discussion with Scholastic science and hundreds (prior to his own) years of observations³⁷. We notice, therefore, that the physics of Copernicus, expressed in his writings, is the modified Christian Aristotelianism³⁸.

³² Cfr: "Terra triplici motu circumfertur", M. Kopernik, *Comentariolus*, p. 11. See also: „Copernicus concluded that Earth has three motions, motivated by his aim to show which apparent celestial motions can be replaced by motions of Earth. As for the apparent motion of the Sun and fixed stars, the Sun's annual motion, the universe's daily rotation, and precession of the equinoxes can be replaced by respectively three motions of Earth", A. Goddu, *Copernicus and the Aristotelian Tradition*, op. cit., p. 247.

³³ Cfr: "Quo etiam Sole immobili permanente, quicquid de motu Solis apparet, hoc potius in mobilitate terrae verificari", M. Kopernik, *De revolutionibus*, lib. I, cap. 10.

³⁴ Cfr: "Careful reading of *Revolut.* proves in its numerous passages that phenomena of the aforementioned motion [Earth axis] attracted him draw more his attention", L. A. Birkenmajer, *Mikolaj Kopernik*, op. cit., p. 214.

³⁵ Cfr: "Even there exists an essential observational equivalence of models of Copernicus and Ptolemy for short-term motions of planets we cannot talk about the one with regard to long-term phenomena", J. Ravetz, *Astronomia i kosmologia w dziele Kopernika*, transl. J. Dobrzycki, Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich Wydawnictwo Polskiej Akademii Nauk, Wrocław 1965, p. 9.

³⁶ Cfr: "Perhaps he intended *Commentariolus* as his brief version of the more popular and less technical works like Peurbach's *Theoricae novae* or Albert of Brudzewo's *Commentariolum*, both of which could be used as texts in university instruction", A. Goddu, *Copernicus and the Aristotelian Tradition*, op. cit., p. 244; and also: „since [Wojciech de] Brudzewo was the most famous astronomer among Cracow teachers and his *Commentariolum* would have been used in teaching and circulated among students, even when he was not teaching it himself, it is certain that Copernicus was familiar with the *Commentariolum super Theoricas novas* from the very beginning of his studies", M. Vesel, *Copernicus*, op. cit., p. 277.

³⁷ Cfr: "My Teacher and Master [Copernicus] undertook the task even more difficult than that of Ptolemy as he had to grasp infallibly in an internally non-contradictory union or harmony multiplicity all motions that during 2000 years were discovered through observations and serve as perfect guides onto the vast area of astronomy", J. J. Retyk, *Relacja pierwsza*, op. cit., p. 89.

³⁸ Cfr: "Copernicus (...) undoubtedly was closer to the Aristotle views, although all contradictions that occur. Aristotelian laws of physics set at the foundation of his theory", R. S. Ingarden, *Mikolaj Kopernik i zagadnienie obiektywności praw naukowych*, op. cit., p. 62.

For those who in their reasoning employ categories of modern physics, it is easier to accept the statement that it is a tiny Earth that moves under the enormous heaven, rather than otherwise, that enormous heaven moves under the little Earth. According to the categories of Aristotle, the stance was as follows: there was a noticeable lack of a factor able to move the heavy Earth, whereas heaven consisting of a weightless aether moved easily³⁹. For the Earth to be movable, a modification of the Aristotelian conception of natural places was needed for each element, and replaced by the relative conception which says that each spheric body is its own centre of the universe. Instead of an explanation based on a natural movement of objects consisting of aether around a heavy immobile centre of the universe, it was reasonable to implement a notion of the fixed motion of each planet around a central Sun, prescribed to

it by the Creator at the beginning of the world. Hence, the modified idea of impetus served this purpose perfectly⁴⁰. The previous model remained in its claim that the Cosmos is a huge sphere of finite dimensions. Externally, both the universe of Copernicus and the universe of Ptolemy in their entirety were huge spheres⁴¹. The other element of previous cosmology adopted by Copernicus, was the idea, that each motion in the sky is a circular motion, or consists of several such motions⁴². The 15th century was equipped with more advanced tools for measurements of the motion of celestial bodies than previous epochs, therefore the Copernican model had to be more complicated than that of Ptolemy, in order to decompose all motions into simple components. In a quantitative sense, that model was more complicated (48 circles in Copernicus, whereas 40 in Ptolemy)⁴³, because its simplicity has a quantitative charac-

³⁹ Cfr: "Within the frame of the Aristotelian physics the process of making a heavy lazy Earth movable was a gigantic undertaking whereas all heaven bodies which were thought to have been consisted of subtle weightless substance would move comparably easily as their movement supposed to be in accordance with their nature", H. Butterfield, *Rodowód współczesnej nauki*, op. cit., p. 32.

⁴⁰ Cfr: "Copernicus applied a kind of theory of *impetus* (...). He did so when dealing with the motions of celestial bodies as well of «celestial» ones, including the earth which was treated as a planet, when drawing all the above conclusions, he followed Buridan (mainly) and the Buridanists (such as Albert of Saxony)", M. Kokowski, *Copernicus's originality: towards integration of contemporary Copernican studies*, Wydawnictwa IHN PAN, Warsaw 2004, p. 56.

⁴¹ Cfr: "Altissimum visibilium omnium, caelum fixarum stellarum esse, neminem video dubitare", M. Kopernik, *De revolutionibus*, lib. I, cap. 10.

⁴² Cfr: "Multitudinem orbium caelestium maiores nostros eam maxime ob causam posuisse video, ut apparentem in sideribus motum sub regularitate salvarent. Valde enim absurdum videbatur caeleste corpus in absolutissima rotunditate non semper aequo moveri. Fieri autem posse animadverterant, ut et compositione atque concursu motuum regularium diversimode ad aliquem situm moveri quippiam videretur, M. Kopernik, *Commentariolus*, s. 10; "Motus corporum coelestium sit aequalis ac circularis, perpetuus, vel ex circularibus compositus", M. Kopernik, *De revolutionibus*, lib. I, cap. 4, titulus.

⁴³ Cfr: "With regard to apparent motions of the Sun and planets both systems [Copernican and Ptolemaic] are equal and Ptolemaic is even less complicated", T. Kuhn, *Przewrót kopernikański*, op. cit., p. 193; „Ptolemy's theory of motion perception is completely identical to Copernicus'. Motion

ter⁴⁴. What is more, in his theory Copernicus explained various phenomena which up to date had their different, even conflicting, explanations. Therefore, we may say that his research programme (according to Lakatos) was more concise, homogenous⁴⁵. The rule of the economy- of simple natural tools (*Sagax naturae*)- known to Cracow Scholastics encouraged Copernicus to search for simple causes accordingly⁴⁶, instead of adopting presumptions⁴⁷. Moreover, heliocentrism appeared to have been more creative, as it much

more sufficiently explained phenomena inexplicable on the ground of geocentrism⁴⁸. If that modification of the Aristotelian physics allowed to construct a model in accordance to an observation, it shows then that the Polish scholar successfully reconciled physics and cosmology⁴⁹.

The fascinating question of how Copernicus came to the heliocentric model of the world was posed numerous times⁵⁰. To answer in the most concise way we need to take into consideration the following inspirations which were:

perception is a matter of relationship. The same apparent motion of an observed object can be perceived both when the observer moves and the observed object is at rest and when the observer is stationary and the observed object moves. Ptolemy explicitly asserts that the latter phenomena of motion are illusions”, M. Vesel, *Copernicus*, op. cit., p. 146.

⁴⁴ Difficulties in description of motions of Moon and Mercure in the Ptolemaic system are among motives Copernicus listed when considering his reflection on a novel model of Cosmos, which would be more systematized: „et ratio inaequalitatis apparentis reddatur constantior”, M. Kopernik, *De revolutionibus*, lib. V, cap. 2.

⁴⁵ Cfr: “Differences about the order of the spheres, the rates of rotation of the celestial spheres, and the variations in the distances of celestial bodies from Earth played a significant role in leading Copernicus to reconsider the proper ordering of the spheres”, A. Goddu, *Copernicus and the Aristotelian Tradition*, op. cit., p. 130.

⁴⁶ Cfr: “Copernicus’ system offers conceptual simplicity rather than arithmetical one”, T. Sierotowicz, *Mikołaj Kopernik*, Wydawnictwo WAM, Kraków 2005, p. 53.

⁴⁷ Cfr: “Sed naturae sagacitas magis sequenda est, quae sicut maxime cavet superfluum quiddam, vel inutile produxisse, ita potius unam saepe rem multis ditavit effectibus”, M. Kopernik, *De revolutionibus*, lib. I, cap. 10. Similarly claimed Wojciech of Brudzewo when he said that: „Sagax natura salvationem rebus inferioribus providens”, quoted by: L. A. Birkenmajer, *Stromata Copernicana. Studia, poszukiwania i materiały biograficzne*, Polska Akademia Umiejętności Kraków 1924, p. 86.

⁴⁸ Cfr: “Copernicus’ programme was novel theoretically only. He predicted new facts never observed before. He predicted phases of Venus. He also predicted star paralax although it was only qualitative predicting”, Cfr: I. Lakatos, E. Zahar, *Dlaczego program badawczy Kopernika wyparł program Ptolemeusza?*, [in:] I. Lakatos, *Pisma z filozofii nauk empirycznych*, ed. W. Sady, Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN, Warszawa 1995, p. 311-312.

⁴⁹ Cfr: “There is consensus now among scholars that Copernicus believed in the existence and reality of (at least) the total spheres that moved the planets. In line with the astronomical and cosmological tradition of the late Middle Ages and Renaissance, Copernicus considered the planetary motions dependent on the motions of real, material spheres in the Ptolemaic and Aristotelian traditions”, M. Vesel, *Copernicus*, op. cit. p. 63.

⁵⁰ Cfr: “As far as we know, Copernicus never recounted the process that led him to those [i.e. heliocentric] conclusions. About thirty years after he proposed a heliocentric theory, the reasons that he provided may represent the evolution of his thought”, A. Goddu, *Copernicus and the Aristotelian Tradition*, op. cit., p. 327.

philosophical motives, mathematical reflection and the religious view that there is an order of the world created by God⁵¹. Philosophical motives are found in a conviction that there exists, available to human cognition, hierarchical, geometrical and physical order in the world reasonably created by God. Mathematical reflection discovers these rules in the process of gathering and selecting observations, and also predicting the future phenomena on the sky. Religious views are these which confirm the existence of laws of the order governing the world according to the Sacred Scripture and the teaching of the Church. Copernicus got acquainted with the Catholic doctrine during his education and service in the Varmian diocese as a canon, regularly involved in activities of the liturgical year. All the aforementioned inspirations were nourished by the Polish scholar in the light of the centennial tradition of development in astronomy whose knowledge he acquainted through the assembled scientific literature, for the most part in Latin.

The significant motif to initiate the reform of astronomy by Copernicus was the need for improvement of the Christian calendar⁵². Thus we notice how the efforts of Church officials to calculate the Tropical year more accurately influenced the research conducted by the astronomer from Frombork (German-Frauenburg)⁵³.

Astronomy requires an enormous amount of time: results of research are visible when conducted by many generations. To gather a sufficient deal of information and ideas for its reform there are needed many centuries to collect data, calculate them into one measure of time and position and then compare various results, as various processes in the sky take place slowly in the course of time, and they tend to be described in various ways. In astronomer's work observation and reflection are both important, because they effect on a theoretical model (*ratione et sensu*)⁵⁴. The approach of Copernicus was documented in detail almost personally

⁵¹ Cfr: "Copernicus in his reasoning was led by philosophical criteria. He reached his heliocentric idea (as he wrote in his youth work) «ratione postea equidem sensu»; not observation but discovering logical contradiction in the system of Ptolemy was a starting point in his analysis which led to new astronomy. Hence his work, in a dedication letter to the Pope Paul III was dedicated to be judged by «philosophers». And on the other hand his astronomy transformed the view on the construction of the universe, the place of the Earth and human being in it, what is a great philosophical achievement", W. Tatarkiewicz, *Historia filozofii*, vol. II, ed. 12, Wydawnictwo PWN, Warszawa 1990, p. 37.

⁵² The reform of the calendar was officially conducted by the pope Gregory XIII (1572-1585) in 1582 and it functions nowadays known as the Gregorian Calendar (although at the beginning there were protests from the part of Protestants and the Eastern Orthodoxy).

⁵³ Cfr: "(...) That what Copernicus started his construction work with. They were phenomenon of motion of the so called the eighth sphere, in other words precession – retrograde motion of the equinoctial points, that is precession, on which depends the fundamental measurement for the entire astronomy: the duration of the sidereal year", L. A. Birkenmajer, *Mikolaj Kopernik*, op. cit., p. 302.

⁵⁴ Cfr: "Talem sane circulorum compositionem tamquam consentientem Lunaribus apparentiis assumpserunt priores. Verum si rem ipsam diligentius expenderimus, non aptam satis nec sufficientem hanc inveniimus hypothesim. Quod ratione et sensu possumus comprobare", M. Kopernik, *De revolutionibus*, lib. IV, cap. 2.

by Rheticus, the witness of his Master's work⁵⁵.

New Copernican view of the world encountered obstacles when paved its way in science⁵⁶, as it was not intuitive⁵⁷, further, it lacked a sensual and empirical verification, and it was not in accordance with simple experiments, traditional Aristotelianism and common Biblical exegesis⁵⁸. Such demanding challenge toward the medieval culture, or to the entire science expressed by the

Polish scholar must not have brought a revolution in each domain of science⁵⁹. The major change in the view of the universe was hence possible with sole modification of presumptions, there was no need to reject them entirely. Previous rules of science remained in force⁶⁰. As a result, there appeared an amazing model of the Cosmos: in the middle there is (*residet*) Sun whereas and the end of the enormous globe of the physical universe there are just fixed stars⁶¹. It

⁵⁵ Cfr: "My Doctor and Master always has in mind observations of all epochs categorized and ordered with his ones as in a catalogue. When hence implications are needed or contribution to science and its laws he proceeds from the prior observations to his own ones and considers arguments whether these are in agreement. Next, results he gained under the conduct of Urania, he compares with hypothesis of Ptolemy and the ancient ones. When after the most detailed analysis possible of these hypotheses he assumes that on the basis of astronomical need he is obliged to reject them, then following a divine inspiration and the will of heaven he adopts novel hypotheses; next drawing on mathematics he works out implications in geometry; finally ancient observations and that of his own he compares with adopted hypotheses and only after finishing all these procedures he writes down the laws of astronomy", J. J. Retyk, *Relacja pierwsza*, op. cit., p. 116.

⁵⁶ "A choice between the system of Copernicus or that of Ptolemy could for astronomers only be a matter of intuition", T. Kuhn, *Przewrót kopernikański*, op. cit., p. 202.

⁵⁷ Cfr: "Regarding the imaginations of world the Aristotelian system was incomparably closer to primordial ideas than the competitive ancient systems and also closer to direct sensual phenomena. This is why it had such an enormous influence especially in the late medieval ages", T. Kuhn, *Przewrót kopernikański*, op. cit., p. 124.

⁵⁸ Cfr: "Copernicus was aware of the passages in the Sacred Scripture who seem to contradict the heliocentric theory, especially of the famous fragment of the Book of Joshua: «Sta Sol et contra Gabaon ne movearis». He however, neglected them and never thought of that fact as of any possible damage to his theory", A. Kempf, *Głos w dyskusji*, [in:] *Mikołaj Kopernik. Studia i materiały sesji kopernikowskiej w KUL 18-19 lutego 1972 roku*, ed. M. Kurdziałek, J. Rebeta, S. Swieżawski, Wydawnictwo Towarzystwa Naukowego Katolickiego Uniwersytetu Lubelskiego, Lublin 1973, p. 241.

⁵⁹ Even opponents admitted that Copernicus is "Astronomiae restitutor egregius, quem tota posteritas grato semper animo, tamquam alterum Ptolemeum calebravit et admirabitur", C. Clavius, *In Sphaeram Ioannis de Sacrobosco Commentarius*, ed. 4, Lyon 1593, s. 67, quoted by J. Ravetz, *Astronomia i kosmologia w dziele Kopernika*, op. cit., p. 47, ref. 12.

⁶⁰ Cfr: "Aristotle's description of the universe as perfect, complete, beautiful, good, and thus worthy of admiration (*Metaphysics* XII, 7) accords with Copernicus's praise of astronomy in *De revolutionibus* I, Introduction", A. Goddu, *Copernicus and the Aristotelian Tradition*, op. cit., p. 401.

⁶¹ Cfr: "In medio vero omnium residet Sol", M. Kopernik, *De revolutionibus*, lib. I, cap. 10. This sentence is the shortest summary of the Copernican theory we may find in the work of Polish astronomer. See also: "Omnes orbes ambire Solem tamquam in medio omnium existentem, ideoque circa Solem esse centrum mundi", M. Kopernik, *Commentariolus*, tertia petitio, p. 10; J. Dreyer, *A History of Astronomy*, op. cit., p. 343; "His [Copernicus'] teaching became the universal view of the Cosmos whose powerful centre was the Sun. That is why his teaching was full of harmony

is worth mentioning that the intuition concerning a particular place of the Sun was present in medieval culture and it is not solely a thesis of the Renaissance origin⁶². On the basis of various insights, also the aforementioned Pythagorean writings, Copernicus was able to gather in one theory a great number of inspirations⁶³.

Each astronomer in the Copernican times could easily testify to the heliocentric model in empirical verification, whose laws were already known to Aristotle. Hence, it was necessary to check

whether stars show an annual motion (parallax), caused by the annual motion of the Earth around the Sun. Until the 19th century the result of such verification was negative⁶⁴. Tycho de Brahe (1546-1601), a renowned Danish astronomer⁶⁵, failed in an attempt to calculate the yearly parallax of the stars. A drawing by Copernicus presented in his own work was of a general character only: the proportion between radius of the circle⁶⁶ of the Earth and the distance from the Sun to the closest star is actually 1: 270 000 and cannot be drawn in the scale

and joy”, B. Suchodolski, *Stońce świata, czyli znaczenie Kopernika w rozwoju nauk o przyrodzie i człowieku*, [w:] *Mikołaj Kopernik. Studia i materiały*, op. cit., p. 117. Also for example, a scholastic philosopher John of Glogovia (Jan z Głogowa) called the Sun “dignissimus planeta, ergo etiam eius influentia est nobilior”, quoted by: L. A. Birkenmajer, *Stromata Copernicana*, op. cit., p. 125.

⁶² The medieval literature offers numerous views that „the Sun produces the most noble metal- gold- and is both the eye and the brain of the entire universe”, C. S. Lewis, *Odrzucony obraz. Wprowadzenie do literatury średniowiecznej i renesansowej*, transl. W. Ostrowski, Instytut Wydawniczy PAX, Warszawa 1986, p. 79. Also, St. Thomas Aquinas distinguished the Sun with regard to its power, influence and organizing the movement of the other planets. He remained however on the ground of geocentrism. Cfr: “sol maior est quantitate inter omnes planetas, et eius effectus magis apparet in rebus inferioribus; et etiam motus aliorum planetarum ordinantur per motum solis, et quodammodo consequuntur ipsum. Unde videtur quod substantia quae movet solem, sit nobilior substantiis quae movent alios planetas, cum tamen sol non sit super omnes alios planetas”, St. Thomas Aquinas, *In duodecim libros Metaphysicorum Aristotelis expositio (Sententia libri Metaphysicae)*, ed. R. Cathala, R. Spiazzi, ed. 1, Taurini 1950, lib. 12, l. 9, n. 8.

⁶³ Cfr: “Nicolai Copernicus Mikołaj Kopernik focused his attention and academic inquisitiveness on the Pythagorean theory of the middle. On that basis he shown that only one element of universe fits to the Pythagorean central fire: it is the Sun”, M. Kurdziałek, *Średniowieczne stanowiska*, dz. cyt., [in:] *Mikołaj Kopernik. Studia i materiały*, op. cit., p. 99; already in the medieval geocentric a role of the Sun was significant: “Their system is in a sense more heliocentric than ours. The Sun illuminates the entire universe. It is said that all stars – says [St.] Isidor [of Seville, 6th/7th century] (...) – they do not possess their own light, but like the Moon are illuminated by the Sun”, D. S. Lewis, *Odrzucony obraz*, op. cit., p. 82.

⁶⁴ Cfr: “Copernicus could not have offered any proofs for the claim that Earth rotates around its axis moves around the Sun. These proofs (...) were gained much later”, E. Rybka, *Astronomia ogólna*, ed. VII, Warszawa 1983, p. 149; “Discovery of star parallax by Bessel was a decisive experiment between two theories [Ptolemy and Copernicus]”, Cfr: I. Łakatos, E. Zahar, *Dlaczego program badawczy Kopernika wyparł program Ptolemeusza?*, op. cit., p. 292.

⁶⁵ Cfr: A description in a Polish encyclopedia of the 18th century: B. Chmielowski, *Nowe Ateny albo Akademia wszelkiej scjencji pełna, na różne tytuły jak na classes podzielona*, vol. I, ed. 2, Lwów 1755, p. 170.

⁶⁶ We use the English term “circle” as translated from the Latin circularum as the “orbit” commonly used can be properly employed in this context since J. Kepler only.

of a drawing, even if significantly underestimated. Against common opinions, the Copernican model was not a process of degradation of the Earth and human being as its inhabitant, but rather elevating the ones from the inferior place in the changing imperfect middle of the world to the level of one of the stars⁶⁷.

* * *

In summarizing the conducted research we may state that in the most general sense, Nicolaus Copernicus essentially was a systematically educated Scholastic and medieval philosopher, an open Scholastic mind of the late Middle Ages⁶⁸. Attempting to conduct a closer research on various impacts and inspirations which influenced his reflection allows to formulate the following general assessment: the philosophy of Copernicus

is medieval in three quarters and Renaissance one in one quarter. In three quarters it is Scholastic and traditional while in one quarter – novel. Obviously, it was the novelty that seems decisive for the recognition and further gradual success of the Polish astronomer. Nonetheless, it was the traditional thought on which novelty developed in paving its way to the refashioned picture of the world. Therefore, we may assume that the physics of Copernicus is the modified Aristotelianism whereas the laws of the order and hierarchy he employs derive from the Christian Platonism and Pythagoreanism⁶⁹. Such estimation is crucial for establishing proportions in a debate with numerous predominating in literature, popular, one-sided views which resonate with misleading opinions and even propaganda⁷⁰.

Transl. Ewa Agnieszka Pichola

⁶⁷ Cfr: A. Lovejoy, *Wielki łańcuch bytu. Studium pewnej idei*, transl. A. Przybysławski, ed. 2 improved, Wydawnictwo Znak, Gdańsk 2009, p. 97; and also “Model [of geocentric Cosmos] is, let us say, anthropoperiphic. We are entities from the margin”, D. S. Lewis, *Odrzucony obraz*, op. cit. p. 49.

⁶⁸ Cfr: “We may infer from Copernicus’s later demonstrated knowledge of numerous authors and subjects that he did receive an education in the liberal arts”, A. Goddu, *Copernicus and the Aristotelian Tradition*, op. cit., p. 18.

⁶⁹ Cfr: “Invenimus igitur hac ordinatione admirandam mundi symmetriam, ac certum harmoniae nexum motus et magnitudinis orbium: qualis alio modo reperiri non potest”, M. Kopernik, *De revolutionibus*, lib. I, cap. 10. See also: “reference to Pythagorean and Stoic philosophy was an important rapid impulse to defend symmetry uniformity and order in the Cosmos. Pythagorean music of spheres demanded mathematically embraced harmony of the universe”, S. Kamiński, *Filozoficzne uwarunkowania rewolucyjnej idei Mikołaja Kopernika*, [in:] *Mikołaj Kopernik. Studia i materiały*, op. cit., p. 128-9.

⁷⁰ Cfr: False opinions present in the Marxists literature: “By the term «Scholasticism» are understood any infertile sophistries detached from life, Talmudism, formalism, as operating with general concepts and abstract assumptions only, regardless the facts and practice. Contemporary bourgeois philosophy revives the medieval Scholasticism in order to achieve a «theoretical justification» of the imperial politics”, *Krótki słownik filozoficzny*, ed. M. Rozentel, P. Judin, Wydawnictwo “Książka i Wiedza”, Warszawa 1955, entry: *Scholastyka*, p. 612.

References:

- Birkenmajer L. A., *Mikołaj Kopernik. Studya nad pracami Kopernika oraz materiały biograficzne*, W Krakowie: skład główny w Księgarni Spółki Wydawniczej Polskiej, Kraków 1900.
- Birkenmajer L. A., *Stromata Copernicana. Studia, poszukiwania i materiały biograficzne*, Kraków 1924.
- Butterfield H., *Rodowód współczesnej nauki 1300-1800*, transl. H. Krahelska, Państwowe Wydawnictwo Naukowe, Warszawa 1963.
- Chmielowski B., *Norwe Ateny albo Akademia wszelkiej scjencji pełna, na różne tytuły jak na classes podzielona*, vol. I, ed. 2, Lwów 1755.
- Couderc P., *Les étapes de l'astronomie*, Presses universitaires de France, Paris 1948.
- Dobrzycki J., *Mikołaj Kopernik* [in:] *Historia astronomii w Polsce*, vol. 1, ed. E. Rybka, Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich, Wrocław 1975.
- Domański J., *Początki humanizmu*, Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich - Wydawnictwo Polskiej Akademii Nauk, Wrocław 1982 (*Dzieje filozofii średniowiecznej w Polsce*, vol. IX).
- Drewnowski J., *Mikołaj Kopernik w świetle swej korespondencji*, Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich - Wydawnictwo Polskiej Akademii Nauk, Wrocław 1978 (*Studia Copernicana*, vol. XVIII).
- Dreyer J., *A History of Astronomy from Thales to Kepler*, 2 ed., Dover Publications, New York 1953.
- Duhem P., *Le système du monde. Histoire des doctrines cosmologiques de Platon a Copernic*, vol. I, Librairie Scientifique Hermann, Paris 1913.
- Goddu A., *Copernicus and the Aristotelian Tradition. Education, Reading, and Philosophy in Copernicus's Path to Heliocentrism*, Brill, Leiden 2010.
- Ingarden R. S., *Mikołaj Kopernik i zagadnienie obiektywności praw naukowych*, Państwowy Instytut Wydawniczy, Warszawa 1953.
- Karas M., *Poglądy filozoficzne Mikołaja Kopernika*, Kraków 2018.
- Kokowski M., *Copernicus's originality: towards integration of contemporary Copernican studies*, Wydawnictwa IHN PAN, Warsaw 2004.
- Kopernik M., *Commentariolus*, [in:] Idem., *Pisma pomniejszych (Dzieła wszystkie, vol. III)*, Wydawnictwo PWN, Warszawa 2007, p. 10-29.
- Kopernik M., *O obrotach*, transl. M. Brożek, S. Oświęcimski, [in:] Idem., *Dzieła wszystkie, vol. II*, Wydawnictwo PWN, Warszawa 1976.
- Krótki słownik filozoficzny*, ed. M. Rozentel, P. Judin, Wydawnictwo „Książka i Wiedza”, Warszawa 1955, entry: *Scholastyka*.
- Kuhn T., *Przewrót kopernikański. Astronomia planetarna w dziejach myśli*, przeł. S. Amsterdamski, Wydawnictwo PWN, Warszawa 1966.
- Lakatos I., Zahar E., *Dlaczego program badawczy Kopernika wyparł program Ptolemeusza?*, [in:] I. Lakatos, *Pisma z filozofii nauk empirycznych*, ed. W. Sady, Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN, Warszawa 1995.

- Lewis C. S., *Odrzucony obraz. Wprowadzenie do literatury średniowiecznej i renesansowej*, transl. W. Ostrowski, Instytut Wydawniczy PAX, Warszawa 1986.
- Lovejoy A., *Wielki łańcuch bytu. Studium pewnej idei*, transl. A. Przybysławski, ed. 2 improved, Wydawnictwo Znak, Gdańsk 2009.
- Malpangotto M., *La critique de l'univers de Peurbach développée par Albert de Brudzewo a-t-elle influencé Copernic? Un nouveau regard sur les réflexions astronomiques au XV-e siècle*, „Almagest. International Journal for the History of Scientific Ideas”, (2013), vol. 4, nr 1, p. 4-61.
- Markowski M., *Burydanizm w Polsce w okresie przedkopernikańskim. Studium z historii filozofii i nauk ścisłych na Uniwersytecie Krakowskim w XV wieku*, Wydawnictwo Ossolineum, Wrocław 1971.
- Mikołaj Kopernik. Studia i materiały sesji kopernikowskiej w KUL 18-19 lutego 1972 roku*, ed. M. Kurdziałek, J. Rebeta, S. Swieżawski, , Wydawnictwo Towarzystwa Naukowego Katolickiego Uniwersytetu Lubelskiego, Lublin 1973.
- Morstin H., *Kłós Panny*, ed. 3, Spółdzielnia Wydawnicza “Wiedza”, Warszawa 1947.
- Nowicki A., *Kopernik człowiek Odrodzenia*, Wydawnictwo Wiedza Powszechna, Warszawa 1953.
- Ravetz J., *Astronomia i kosmologia w dziele Kopernika*, transl. J. Dobrzycki, Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich Wydawnictwo Polskiej Akademii Nauk, Wrocław 1965.
- Retyk J. J., *Relacja pierwsza z ksiąg «O obrotach» Mikołaja Kopernika*, transl. I. Lewandowski, ed. J. Włodarczyk, Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego, Warszawa 2015.
- Rybka E., *Astronomia ogólna*, ed. VII, Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich, Warszawa 1983.
- Sierotowicz T., *Mikołaj Kopernik*, Wydawnictwo WAM, Kraków 2005.
- Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (<https://plato.stanford.edu>), entry: *Albert of Saxony* (2015).
- Swieżawski S., *Dzieje filozofii europejskiej XV wieku*, vol. 5, Warszawa 1980.
- Tatarkiewicz W., *Historia filozofii*, vol. II, ed. 12, Wydawnictwo PWN, Warszawa 1990.
- Thomas Aquinas St., *In duodecim libros Metaphysicorum Aristotelis expositio (Sententia libri Metaphysicae)*, ed. R. Cathala, R. Spiazzi, ed. 1, Taurini 1950.
- Vesel M., *Copernicus: Platonist Astronomer-Philosopher: Cosmic Order, the Movement of the Earth, and the Scientific Revolution*, Peter Lang GmbH, Internationaler Verlag der Wissenschaften, Frankfurt am Main 2014.